

SUPPLEMENT to Deliverable D2.1: “Report on gaps and needs of Stakeholders and Competent Authorities to support the processes for harmonised Ecological Assessment across the Black Sea”

Deliverable D2.1-Supplement

Horizon 2020

H2020-EU.3.2.3.3.

‘Developing Optimal and Open Research Support’
for the Black Sea. (DOORS)

Project Number: 101000518

Supplement to Deliverable No: D2.1		Work Package: WP2	
Date:		Contract delivery due date	
Title:	Report on gaps and needs of Stakeholders and Competent Authorities to support the processes for harmonised Ecological Assessment across the Black Sea		
Lead Partner for Deliverable	HCMR		
Author(s):	Erasmia Kastanidi, Nikos Streftaris, Kalliopi Pagou		
Dissemination level (PU=public, RE=restricted, CO=confidential)			PU
Report Status (DR = Draft, FI = FINAL)			FI
Acknowledgements DOORS has received funding from the from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 Framework Programme for Research and Innovation under grant agreement No 101000518			
Revised on June 2023, Revised on April 2024 Final revision December 2024			

Table of Contents

List of Supplementary Material to D2.1.....	4
1. Affiliated institutions of workshop participants and questionnaire respondents.....	5
2. Workshop’s Invitation letter template.....	7
3. Workshop and Questionnaire Informed consent form	8
4. Agenda of the Workshop:	10
5. The Workshop’s Questionnaire	11
6. The Interviews Questionnaire	44
7. Inventory of available data and methods	53

List of Supplementary material to D2.1

- 1 – Affiliated institutions of workshop participants and questionnaire respondents
- 2 – Workshop Invitation letter template
- 3 – Workshop and Questionnaire Inform consent form
- 4 – Agenda of the Workshop
- 5 – Workshop’s Questionnaire (<https://doc.doorsblacksea.eu/>)
- 6 – Interviews’ Questionnaire
- 7 – Data and methods availability inventory

1. Affiliated institutions of workshop participants and questionnaire respondents

1. Academy of Sciences of Moldova
2. Black sea Basin Directorate
3. Black Sea Institute Association
4. BSC PS
5. Bulgarian Academy of Sciences
6. CNR
7. Department of Materials Science and Engineering, McMaster University
8. Dokuz Eylül University
9. EMBRC-ERIC
10. EMSO ERIC
11. Environmental Engineering Department, Istanbul University-Cerrahpaşa
12. European Environment Agency
13. European Global Ocean Observing System
14. GIS and RS Consulting Center GeoGraphic
15. HCMR
16. Helmholtz Zentrum Hereon
17. IFREMER
18. Institute for Integrated Studies of the National Maritime policy RTU MIREA
19. Institute Geophysics of NASU
20. Institute of Ecology and Geography, Moldova
21. Institute of marine biology of the NAS of Ukraine
22. Institute of Marine Biology, Odessa, Ukraine
23. Institute of oceanology-BAS
24. International Office for water (CA)
25. Istanbul University, Institute of Marine Sciences & Management
26. Iv. Javakhishvili Tbilisi State University
27. LifeWatch ERIC
28. Mare Nostrum NGO
29. MGEC
30. Ministry of Environment. Bulgaria
31. Ministry of Environment Romania
32. Ministry of Environment, Russia
33. Ministry of Environment and Natural Resources Protection of Georgia
34. Ministry of Foreign Affairs, Deputy Director of European Cooperation
35. NANU
36. NAS
37. National Institute for Marine Geology and Geoecology - GeoEcoMar, Romania
38. National Institute for Marine Research "GrigoreAntipa", Constanța, Romania
39. Odessa State Environmental University
40. P.P. Shirshov Institute of Oceanology
41. Plovdiv University
42. Russian State Oceanographic Institute,
43. Sofia University St. Kliment Ohridski
44. SSI MariGeoEcoCenter NASU

45. State Oceanographic Institute, Moscow
46. State Scientific Institution " Center for Problems of Marine Geology, Geoecology and Sedimentary Ore Formations of the National Academy of Sciences "
47. Tiraspol State University
48. Ukrainian Environmental Academy of Science
49. Ukrainian Scientific Center of Ecology of the Sea
50. University of Bucharest

2. Workshop's Invitation letter template

Dear,

With this message we are pleased to invite you to the: "WP2 1st workshop and online consultation with stakeholders and Competent Authorities. Support the processes for harmonised Ecological Assessment across the Black Sea – Step 1: Identification of gaps and needs" of the DOORS project.

The workshop will be held on line on 14th October 2021 and you have been identified by the DOORS project Country Coordinators, as Key stakeholders/experts to participate to the workshop and assist DOORS delivering its results. The objective of this 1st workshop is to map the needs and gaps of the Black Sea Policy Makers and Experts towards the goal to deliver a Manual of Harmonised methods for Marine Ecological Assessment across the Black Sea.

This 1st workshop is based in an on-line questionnaire, which can be found at: https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/DOORS_Data_Needs_Consultation1

Please find attached:

- 1) The DOORS project summary,
- 2) The invitation letter,
- 3) The workshop's agenda,
- 4) The online Questionnaire also as pdf document
(*DOORS_WP2_Workshop_and_Online_Consultation_06_10_2021_EN.pdf*),
- 5) The on-line workshop Participation Informed consent, as a pdf document.

The next days we will also provide you with the meeting link.

Thank you in advance and hope to see you in our DOORS online workshop!

Best regards,

Kalliopi Pagou

DOORS WP2 co-leader

3. Workshop and Questionnaire Informed consent form

**WP2 workshop and online consultation with stakeholders and Competent Authorities. Support the harmonisation processes for existing data and methodologies.
Step 1: Identification of gaps and needs**

(14thOctober 2021)

Data privacy statement

DECLARATION OF CONSENT ACCORDING TO ART. 13 GDPR

The project “DOORS - Developing Optimal and Open Research Support for the Black Sea” (grant agreement no. 101000518) is an EU H2020 - funded innovation action, whose goal is to develop a develop and implement an ecosystem-based framework for Blue Economy, inform policy development and implementation, and promote behavioural change towards sustainability.

In order to achieve this DOORS will work closely with stakeholders and other projects and initiatives in the region, addressing research and infrastructure needs to close the knowledge gaps, and learn from the expertise of different Black Sea stakeholder groups including their knowledges, needs and aspirations in the process.

You were selected and asked to participate in this study because of your background and expertise with national or international environmental policies and monitoring programs.

National partners and their contact networks chose a selection of stakeholders that would be best suited for this setting and research questions in terms of experience and expertise.

We consider you a valuable part of this project as your willingness to share your expertise and experience is critical for the output of the project and for supporting the harmonization process for existing data and methodologies meeting your needs.

During this workshop we will inform you about the DOORS project and through this questionnaire and in parallel with the workshop discussions we will ask you to identify your main challenges and needs in terms of monitoring and assessing the environmental and ecological conditions in the Black Sea. It is voluntary to participate in this study and you may at any time chose to withdraw your consent. By signing the consent box in the questionnaire form, you agree to your personal data with regards to knowledge on the implementation of environmental policies in your country being used in this survey, however any personal information will only be available to the survey holder and the results will be publicized anonymously, with the only reference to the workshop and the questionnaire be with regards to country representation.

Furthermore, it is important to understand that to present our activities as transparently and as comprehensively as possible to the financial funders and the public, selected “DOORS” activities are documented in sound and vision.

By participating in the Workshop “WP2 workshop and online consultation with stakeholders and CAs - Support the harmonisation processes for existing data and methodologies – Step 1: Identification of gaps and needs” taking place on 14th October 2021, you agree to the following:

I hereby agree that the film, sound and photo recordings, as well as any contributions in written form such as but not limited to comments in the Q&A and chat-section of the online video call tool used in the workshop (“the material”), on which I or my contribution to the workshop may appear in sound and vision or in written form, may be used by the coordinator of the project for statutory purposes, in particular for non-commercial scientific purposes, for editorial purposes and for public relations purposes in print products, on websites and in social media, however without making connections between my personal data and my views and opinions.

“DOORS” may pass on the material to third parties only for non-commercial scientific purposes, for editorial reporting in connection with research activities or events of “DOORS”, excluding all personal data.

I have been informed that I can revoke my consent under this agreement at any time and without giving reasons. The revocation refers to future uses only. The contact partner for the revocation is (Kalliopi Pagou - HCMR; *email: popi@hcmr.gr*).

I am aware that it is possible in any moment for any participant to record the material as a picture via screenshot. In the case of a revocation of my consent to a publication, “DOORS” cannot exclude the possibility that my image may be used by third parties despite the deletion from the “DOORS” website or from social media. This also applies to the material that have been passed on to third parties within the scope of this declaration of consent.

I consent that my contact details (First and Last Name, Organisation, Function, Country represented and e-mail) being included in the list of participants and seen by the meeting participants and the collected data (images, videos, evaluation forms, questionnaires etc.) also will be used to reporting to EU Commission in DOORS” reports.

All personal data collected during the implementation of this workshop will be deleted at the latest 5 years after the end of the “DOORS” project on 31.05.2025.

4. Agenda of the Workshop

[Developing Optimal and Open Research Support for the Black Sea](#)

**WP2 - 1st workshop and online consultation with stakeholders and CAs
Support the processes for harmonised Ecological Assessment across the Black Sea
Step 1: Identification of gaps and needs**

Agenda

14 October 2021

Tele meeting

09:30 – 13:00 CEST

- 09:30 - 09:45 **Introduction - Purpose of the meeting**
Dr K. Pagou & Dr N. Fedoronchuk, WP2 co-leaders
- 09:45 - 10:00 The DOORS project
Dr Adrian Stanica Project coordinator
- 10:00 - 11:00 **Marine Environmental Policies Implementation across the Black Sea**
- CA needs on data and policies
- Ideas to establish collaboration and cooperation on the data/information/policies
Discussion with country stakeholder/experts
- 11:00 - 12:30 **The Questionnaire:**
- Presentation
- How to answer it
- Ways to improve it
- Next Steps
- Complete the questionnaire in full in the next few weeks by identifying the experts when and where are needed.
Moderators: Dr E. Kastanidi & Mr N. Strefaris
- 12:30 - 13:00 **Any other business**

5. The Workshop's Questionnaire

The questionnaire can be found also at:

<https://doc.doorsblacksea.eu/index.php/apps/files/?dir=/&fileid=158>

Its text version is Annexed here for easier reference:

Questionnaire to accompany 1st DOORS WP2 workshop and online consultation with stakeholders and CAs.

Fields marked with * are mandatory.

Summary and Scope

The questionnaire has been created to accompany the stakeholders consultation process on identifying what are the main needs of Black Sea countries for implementing environmental policies.

The overall objective, at the end of the consultation process, is to deliver harmonised methodologies for sampling, measurement, analysis and modelling, taking into account best practices on the assessment of the ecological status of the Black Sea and it will be achieved after a series of consultations and workshops. This harmonisation is dedicated to the development of compatible working methodologies that will ensure that all data collection, analysis and storage processes respect, policy requirements, international standards and best practices, as well as the FAIR principles.

The objective of **this 1st workshop** is to map the needs and gaps of the Black Sea Policy Makers and experts towards this goal, in order to assist the next step, the review and comparison of existing regional /subregional methods, methodologies and guidelines. In the series of workshops that will follow, these will be adapted to the BS specificities by proposing harmonised options, which will ensure compatibility with the Black Sea policy requirements for achieving a good ecological status in the area.

The present questionnaire is the first step for receiving feedback from you regarding the above inquires focusing on which Assessment Elements or Objectives can be assessed at a satisfactory level, what data are collected, how these are stored and managed, the field and laboratory methods for obtaining (and analysing data) as well as the assessment methodologies followed. All this information will be helpful for prioritising the most pressing gaps and needs.

The questionnaire is organised in five distinct sections:

1. Respondents Information (used for questionnaire classification only)
2. Marine Environmental Policies Implementation Processes
3. Assessment of gaps and needs (further divided in subsections according to respondent's expertise on data collection methodologies)
4. Assessment methodologies
5. Concluding remarks

Notice: We don't expect you to fill-in all the questionnaire, in fact only the Country of Residence and your role or relationship in International or National programs have been identified as mandatory questions.

However, we kindly ask you to identify other possible colleagues who could be interested in participating in the consultation process.

Furthermore, it is likely that the SH (policy makers & experts) present will not be able to know details of how all parameters and methodologies are being measured, but they are more likely to know who does what, so they can contact the relevant experts, and the questionnaire is expected to be fully answered at a later stage

Please Download Data Privacy Statement before proceeding with the questionnaire

[Workshop Participation Informed Consent.pdf](#)

I have downloaded and read the Workshop Participation Informed Consent and I accept your terms

Respondents Information

(personal data are for statistical use only and will not be disclosed to anyone beyond the person responsible for the survey. – personal data

will be destroyed once all analysis has been completed as described in the above data privacy statement)

Name

Surname

* Email address

Date of Birth

* Country of Residence

- AF - Afghanistan
- AL - Albania
- DZ - Algeria
- AD - Andorra
- AO - Angola
- AG - Antigua and Barbuda
- AR - Argentina
- AM - Armenia
- AU - Australia
- AT - Austria
- AZ - Azerbaijan
- BS - Bahamas

- ⊙ BH - Bahrain
- ⊙ BD - Bangladesh
- ⊙ BB - Barbados
- ⊙ BY - Belarus
- ⊙ BE - Belgium
- ⊙ BZ - Belize
- ⊙ BJ - Benin
- ⊙ BT - Bhutan
- ⊙ BO - Bolivia
- ⊙ BA - Bosnia and Herzegovina
- ⊙ BW - Botswana
- ⊙ BR - Brazil
- ⊙ BN - Brunei Darussalam
- ⊙ BG - Bulgaria
- ⊙ BF - Burkina Faso
- ⊙ BI - Burundi
- ⊙ CV - Cabo Verde
- ⊙ KH - Cambodia
- ⊙ CM - Cameroon
- ⊙ CA - Canada
- ⊙ CF - Central African Republic
- ⊙ TD - Chad
- ⊙ CL - Chile
- ⊙ CN - China
- ⊙ CO - Colombia
- ⊙ KM - Comoros
- ⊙ CG - Congo
- ⊙ CR - Costa Rica
- ⊙ CI - Côte D'Ivoire
- ⊙ HR - Croatia
- ⊙ CU - Cuba
- ⊙ CY - Cyprus
- ⊙ CZ - Czechia
- ⊙ CD - Democratic Republic of the Congo
- ⊙ DK - Denmark
- ⊙ DJ - Djibouti
- ⊙ DM - Dominica
- ⊙ DO - Dominican Republic
- ⊙ EC - Ecuador
- ⊙ EG - Egypt
- ⊙ SV - El Salvador
- ⊙ GQ - Equatorial Guinea
- ⊙ ER - Eritrea
- ⊙ EE - Estonia
- ⊙ SZ - Eswatini
- ⊙ ET - Ethiopia
- ⊙ FJ - Fiji

- FI - Finland
- FR - France
- GA - Gabon
- GM - Gambia
- GE - Georgia
- DE - Germany
- GH - Ghana
- GR - Greece
- GD - Grenada
- GT - Guatemala
- GN - Guinea
- GW - Guinea Bissau
- GY - Guyana
- HT - Haiti
- HN - Honduras
- HU - Hungary
- IS - Iceland
- IN - India
- ID - Indonesia
- IR - Iran
- IQ - Iraq
- IE - Ireland
- IL - Israel
- IT - Italy
- JM - Jamaica
- JP - Japan
- JO - Jordan
- KZ - Kazakhstan
- KE - Kenya
- KI - Kiribati
- KW - Kuwait
- KG - Kyrgyzstan
- LA - Laos
- LV - Latvia
- LB - Lebanon
- LS - Lesotho
- LR - Liberia
- LY - Libya
- LI - Liechtenstein
- LT - Lithuania
- LU - Luxembourg
- MG - Madagascar
- MW - Malawi
- MY - Malaysia
- MV - Maldives
- ML - Mali
- MT - Malta

- ⊙ MH - Marshall Islands
- ⊙ MR - Mauritania
- ⊙ MU - Mauritius
- ⊙ MX - Mexico
- ⊙ FM - Micronesia
- ⊙ MC - Monaco
- ⊙ MN - Mongolia
- ⊙ ME - Montenegro
- ⊙ MA - Morocco
- ⊙ MZ - Mozambique
- ⊙ MM - Myanmar
- ⊙ NA - Namibia
- ⊙ NR - Nauru
- ⊙ NP - Nepal
- ⊙ NL - Netherlands
- ⊙ NZ - New Zealand
- ⊙ NI - Nicaragua
- ⊙ NE - Niger
- ⊙ NG - Nigeria
- ⊙ KP - North Korea
- ⊙ MK - North Macedonia
- ⊙ NO - Norway
- ⊙ OM - Oman
- ⊙ PK - Pakistan
- ⊙ PW - Palau
- ⊙ PA - Panama
- ⊙ PG - Papua New Guinea
- ⊙ PY - Paraguay
- ⊙ PE - Peru
- ⊙ PH - Philippines
- ⊙ PL - Poland
- ⊙ PT - Portugal
- ⊙ QA - Qatar
- ⊙ MD - Republic of Moldova
- ⊙ RO - Romania
- ⊙ RU - Russian Federation
- ⊙ RW - Rwanda
- ⊙ KN - Saint Kitts and Nevis
- ⊙ LC - Saint Lucia
- ⊙ VC - Saint Vincent and the Grenadines
- ⊙ WS - Samoa
- ⊙ SM - San Marino
- ⊙ ST - Sao Tome and Principe
- ⊙ SA - Saudi Arabia
- ⊙ SN - Senegal
- ⊙ RS - Serbia
- ⊙ SC - Seychelles

- SL - Sierra Leone
- SG - Singapore
- SK - Slovakia
- SI - Slovenia
- SB - Solomon Islands
- SO - Somalia
- ZA - South Africa
- KR - South Korea
- SS - South Sudan
- ES - Spain
- LK - Sri Lanka
- SD - Sudan
- SR - Suriname
- SE - Sweden
- CH - Switzerland
- SY - Syrian Arab Republic
- TJ - Tajikistan
- TZ - Tanzania
- TH - Thailand
- TL - Timor-Leste
- TG - Togo
- TO - Tonga
- TT - Trinidad and Tobago
- TN - Tunisia
- TR - Turkey
- TM - Turkmenistan
- TV - Tuvalu
- UG - Uganda
- UA - Ukraine
- AE - United Arab Emirates
- GB - United Kingdom
- US - United States of America
- UY - Uruguay
- UZ - Uzbekistan
- VU - Vanuatu
- VE - Venezuela
- VN - Viet Nam
- YE - Yemen
- ZM - Zambia
- ZW - Zimbabwe

Affiliation (Institution)

• Relation to International/National monitoring programs

Marine Environmental Policies Implementation Progress in Black Sea

Marine Environmental Policies and Programmes (as BSIMAP, MSFD, Blue Growth, etc) base their implementation on monitoring programs to fulfil their objectives to be reached, in order to improve the Ecological Quality Status of the Black Sea. In this frame specific monitoring guidelines and requirements for assessing data and status are needed.

The main task of such programs are to produce quality assured data for scientifically- based and validated indicators to be used by policy-makers, in this case consistent with the environmental quality objectives (EcoQs) of the BS SAP.

Most of the following questions are based on the format of the EcoQOs, descriptors and parameters as set on the BLACK SEA INTEGRATED MONITORING AND ASSESSMENT PROGRAM for years 2017-2022 (BSIMAP 2017-2022). However, these do not differ in essence from the Descriptor and Criteria used in the MSFD or in the EO set by the UNEP/MAP or the other Regional Sea Conventions.

To the best of your knowledge data supporting the upcoming assessment of:

- All Ecological quality objectives
- More than half of the Ecological quality objectives but not all yet but we are on track to complete by the end of this cycle
- Less than half of the Ecological quality objectives yet but we are working on it
- Very few and we are not sure we will reach our goal by the end of this cycle
- I am not sure

According to the best of your knowledge which are the **Assessment Elements** (e.g. Ecological Quality Objectives, MSFD descriptors, Blue Growth potential) that are more difficult to evaluate? (Please 1-5 according to the level of knowledge you are able to acquire for each of the objectives based on the ability to monitor the required parameters? (1 for the least known and 5 for the most known)

	1 (Least known fewer parameters measured)	2	3	4	5 (Most known all required parameters measured)
The State of Populations of all commercially exploited fish and shellfish	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Abundance diversity and reproductive capacity of all elements of the marine food webs to the extent that they are known.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Coastal Area distribution and abundance of species in relation with prevailing physiographic, geographic and climatic conditions and quality and occurrence of habitats for the preservation of biodiversity	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Sea Floor distribution and abundance of species in relation with prevailing physiographic, geographic and climatic conditions and quality and occurrence of habitats for the preservation	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Impacts of introduced non- indigenous species on the BS ecosystems	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Eutrophication and its effects on biodiversity, ecosystem degradation, possible presence of harmful algae blooms and oxygen deficiency in bottom waters	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Concentrations of contaminants in water	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Concentrations of contaminants in fish and other seafood for human consumption	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Properties and quantities of marine litter	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Level of noise and its impacts in the marine ecosystem	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Renewable Energy potential	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Sea-floor integrity is at a level that ensures that the structure and functions of the ecosystems are safeguarded and benthic ecosystems, in particular, are not adversely affected.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Permanent alteration of hydrographical conditions does not adversely affect marine ecosystems.	<input type="checkbox"/>				

To the best of your knowledge what is the most common reason for insufficient assessments?

- Technical difficulties related to monitoring
- Monitoring costs
- Inadequate time series
- Inadequate Assessment methodology
- Lack of threshold values, GES definition etc
- Other (can you define?)

Please define other possible reasons

Do you feel that the above mentioned **Assessment Elements** cover all Black Sea assessment needs or are there more issues that you feel should be identified?

- Above mentioned objectives cover all concerns of the Black Sea
- No there are still concerns on the status of the Black Sea that are not being identified

Please Identify what you feel is missing to complete an assessment on the status of the Black Sea

Assessment on gaps and needs for implementing environmental policies

How satisfied are you with the ability to assess the status of the coastal zone and the open sea, in the Black Sea regions?

Please select 1 to 5 according to the level of knowledge you have based on available data (1 for the least known and 5 for the most known)

	1 (Least Known low data availability)	2	3	4	5 (Mostly known high data availability)
Coastal Zone	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Open Sea	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

To the best of your knowledge is Black Sea related data easily accessible?

- Yes
- No

When interested in assessing the environment of the Black Sea, where do you look for data?

- United Nations or other International data bases
- EModNet and/or other European data bases
- Black Sea Commission Database
- National data bases
- University/research center's database
- Request from owners (past researchers)
- I don't know

To the best of your knowledge how easy is it for you to access the available data?

- Most of the data are located in easy to use databases and can be downloaded
- Some of the data can be downloaded the rest are easily available upon request
- Most of the data are in known locations but are not easy to access
- Most of the data are not accessible or their location is unknown.

Do you monitor climate change in your area?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

Please identify which aspects of Climate Change you monitor

- Extreme events (eg floods, heatwaves, wildfires)
- Accelerated coastal erosion
- Accelerated sea level rise
- Sea temperature
- Acidification
- Other

The following section is organised to identify specific needs on the different Assessment Elements. Please choose the most relevant according to your expertise to provide more detailed information on the data and methods for each of the identified parameters.

Please select which of the following relate better to your expertise and your knowledge on the status of data collection methodologies in order to answer the most suitable questions

- Preservation of commercial marine living resources
- Conservation of Black Sea Biodiversity and Habitats
- Coastal Zone Dynamics and its Management
- Eutrophication
- Pollutants originating from land based sources, including inputs from rivers
- Pollutants originating from shipping activities and offshore installations
- Seafloor and coastal sediments
- None of the above, I am not a data expert (involved in policy implementation)**

Please define expertise

Preserve commercial marine living resources

Please provide more detailed information on the data collected for each parameter required of the assessment of the Ecological Quality Objectives according to your expertise

Parameters (as in BSIMAP 2017-22)	Data availability (select most appropriate) 1. Not able to collect data for 2. Recently implemented - no data yet 3. Sporadic / random data available 4. Good data availability	Time series (Please identify range of available data series)	Frequency of data collection (select most appropriate) 1. Annually 2. Seasonally 3. Monthly 4. Weekly 5. Daily 6. Hourly 7. Continuous 8. Other	Framework/Project (national – international)	N/A
Fish landing (annually)					
Fishing effort					
Catch per Unit effort					
Fish stocks (annually)					
Stock Biomass					
Spawning stock biomass					
Proportion of fish larger than the mean size of first sexual maturation					
Status of trophic base					
Recruitment and abundance of juveniles in different habitats					
Aquaculture production					
Number of fishing free zones					
Name and number of stocks below biological safety limits					
Specimens of Black Sea bottlenose dolphins in captivity					

11

Can you please provide more information and possible links to known databases where the above mentioned data are stored?

12

Can you please provide more detailed information on the field and laboratory methodologies for obtaining data?

PARAMETER (as in BSIMAP 2017-22)	Monitoring station network (station grid)	Sampling area (region subregion etc, coastal, open sea)	Sampling Methodological standards	Field Sampling method (e.g. CTD) if possible add ref	Laboratory methods (e.g. fluometric)	Framework/Project (national – international)
Fish landing (annually)						
Fishing effort						
Fish stocks (annually)						
Aquaculture production						
Number of fishing free zones						
Name and number of stocks below biological safety limits						
Specimens of Black Sea bottlenose dolphins in captivity						
Fish landing (annually)						
Fishing effort						

Conservation of Black Sea Biodiversity and Habitats

Please provide more detailed information on the data collected for each parameter required of the assessment of the Ecological Quality Objectives according to your expertise

Parameters (as in BSIMAP 2017-22)	Data availability (select most appropriate) 1. Not able to collect data for 2. Recently implemented - no data yet 3. Sporadic / random data available 4. Good data availability	Time series (Please identify range of available data series)	Frequency of data collection (select most appropriate) 1. Annually 2. Seasonally 3. Monthly 4. Weekly 5. Daily 6. Hourly 7. Continuous 8. Other	Framework/Project (national – international)	N/A
Chl a					
Phytoplankton					
Mesozooplankton					
Biomass of Noctiluca					
Macrophytobenthos					
Macrozoobenthos					
Number and names of introduced non- indigenous species					
Number and names of newly introduced threatened species					

Can you please provide more information and possible links to known databases where the above mentioned data are stored?

Can you please provide more detailed information on the field and laboratory methodologies for obtaining data?

PARAMETER (as in BSIMAP 2017-22)	Monitoring station network (station grid)	Sampling area (region subregion etc, coastal, open sea)	Sampling Methodological standards	Field Sampling method (e.g. CTD) If possible add ref	Laboratory methods (e.g. fluorometric)	Framework/Project (national – international)
Chl a						
Phytoplankton						
Mesozooplankton						
Biomass of Noctiluca						
Macrophytobenthos						
Macrozoobenthos						
Number and names of introduced non- indigenous species						

Reduce eutrophication

18

Please provide more detailed information on the data collected for each parameter required of the assessment of the Ecological Quality Objectives according to your expertise

Parameters (as in BSIMAP 2017:22)	Data availability (select most appropriate) 1. Not able to collect data for 2. Recently implemented - no data yet 3. Sporadic / random data available 4. Good data availability	Time series (Please identify range of available data series)	Frequency of data collection (select most appropriate) 1. Annually 2. Seasonally 3. Monthly 4. Weekly 5. Daily 6. Hourly 7. Continuous 8. Other	Framework/Project (national – international)	N/A
Salinity					
O2 (saturation and dissolved)					
TSS (filter 0.45 µm)					
Transparency Secchi					
P (PO4)					
P total					
N (NH4)					
N (NO3)					
N (NO2)					
N _{total}					
Si (SiO4)					
Cl a					
pH					
BOD5					

19

Can you please provide more information and possible links to known databases where the above mentioned data are stored?

20

Can you please provide more detailed information on the field and laboratory methodologies for obtaining data?

PARAMETER (as in BSIMAP 2017-22)	Monitoring station network (station grid)	Sampling area (region subregion etc, coastal, open sea)	Sampling Methodological standards	Field Sampling method (e.g. CTD) If possible add ref	Laboratory methods (e.g. fluometric)	Framework/Project (national – international)
Salinity M						
O2 (saturation and dissolved)						
TSS (filter 0.45 µm) M						
Transparency Secchi						
P (PO4)						
P total						
N (NH4)						
N (NO3)						
N (NO2)						
N, Total						
Si (SiO4)						
Cl a						
pH						
BOD5						

21

Reduce pollutants originating from land based sources, including river inputs

Please provide more detailed information on the data collected for each parameter required of the assessment of the Ecological Quality Objectives according to your expertise

Parameters (as in BSIMAP 2017-22)	Data availability (select most appropriate) 1. Not able to collect data for 2. Recently implemented - no data yet 3. Sporadic / random data available 4. Good data availability	Time series (Please identify range of available data series)	Frequency of data collection (select most appropriate) 1. Annually 2. Seasonally 3. Monthly 4. Weekly 5. Daily 6. Hourly 7. Continuous 8. Other	Framework/Project (national – international)	N/A
Water and Sediment					
Oil pollution					
Petroleum Hydrocarbons					
Heavy Metals					
Oil slicks					
Heavy metals					
Cd					
Cu					
Hg					
Pb					
Fe					
Zn					
Cr					
Ni					
Mn					
Lindane op (organochlorine pesticides)					

23

Phenols volatile					
Phenol chlorinated					
Detergents					
PAHs					
¹³⁷ Cs					
⁹⁰ Sr					
Marine litter (specific, to be developed)					
Noise level (specific, to be developed)					
Others					
Bathing water Quality					
Total Coliforms					
Fecal Coliforms					
Fecal Streptococci					

24

Can you please provide more information and possible links to known databases where the above mentioned data are stored?

Can you please provide more detailed information on the field and laboratory methodologies for obtaining data?

PARAMETER (as in BSIMAP 2017-22)	Monitoring station network (station grid)	Sampling area (region subregion etc, coastal, open sea)	Sampling Methodological standards	Field Sampling method (e.g. CTD) If possible add ref	Laboratory methods (e.g. fluometric)	Framework/Project (national – international)
Oil pollution						
Petroleum Hydrocarbons						
Heavy Metals						
Oil slicks						
Heavy metals						
Cd						
Cu						
Hg						
Pb						
Fe						
Zn						
Cr						
Ni						
Mn						
Lindane op (organochlorine pesticides)						
Phenols volatile						
Phenol chlorinated						
Detergents						
PAHs						
137Cs						
90Sr						
Marine litter (specific, to be developed)						

26

Noise level (specific, to be developed)						
Others						
Total Coliforms						
Fecal Coliforms						
Fecal Streptococci						

27

Reduce pollutants originating from shipping activities and offshore installations

28

Please provide more detailed information on the data collected for each parameter required of the assessment of the Ecological Quality Objectives according to your expertise

Parameters (as in BSIMAP 2017-22)	Data availability (select most appropriate) 1. Not able to collect data for 2. Recently implemented - no data yet 3. Sporadic / random data available 4. Good data availability	Time series (Please identify range of available data series)	Frequency of data collection (select most appropriate) 1. Annually 2. Seasonally 3. Monthly 4. Weekly 5. Daily 6. Hourly 7. Continuous 8. Other	Framework/Project (national – international)	N/A
Accidental spills					
Illegal discharges (oil and others)					
Number, amounts and locations of accidental and illegal pollution / spills					
Actual load of PRFs (garbage, sewage and oil)					

29

Can you please provide more information and possible links to known databases where the above mentioned data are stored?

Can you please provide more detailed information on the field and laboratory methodologies for obtaining data?

PARAMETER (as in BSIMAP 2017-22)	Monitoring station network (station grid)	Sampling area (region subregion etc, coastal, open sea)	Sampling Methodological standards	Field Sampling method (e.g. CTD) If possible add ref	Laboratory methods (e.g. fluorimetric)	Framework/Project (national – international)	G
Accidental spills							
Illegal discharges (oil and others)							
Number, amounts and locations of accidental and illegal pollution / spills							
Actual load of PRFs (garbage, sewage and oil)							

Sea floor and coastal sediment data

32

Please provide more detailed information on the data collected for each parameter required of the assessment of the Ecological Quality Objectives according to your expertise

Parameters (as in BSIMAP 2017:22)	Data availability (select most appropriate) 1. Not able to collect data for 2. Recently implemented - no data yet 3. Sporadic / random data available 4. Good data availability	Time series (Please identify range of available data series)	Frequency of data collection (select most appropriate) 1. Annually 2. Seasonally 3. Monthly 4. Weekly 5. Daily 6. Hourly 7. Continuous 8. Other	Framework/Project (national – international)	N/A
Typology of coastal and sea floor sediments / including petrology of hard rock substrate					
Grain size of coastal and sea floor sediments					
Mineralogy of coastal and sea floor sediments					
Geochemical parameters of the sea floor sediments					
Gases in the seafloor sediments (CH ₄ , H ₂ S, CO ₂ , O ₂)					

33

Can you please provide more information and possible links to known databases where the above mentioned data are stored?

34

Can you please provide more detailed information on the field and laboratory methodologies for obtaining data?

PARAMETER (as in BSIMAP 2017/22)	Monitoring station network (station grid)	Sampling area (region subregion etc, coastal, open sea)	Sampling Methodological standards	Field Sampling method (e.g. CTD) If possible add ref	Laboratory methods (e.g. fluorimetric)	Framework/Project (national – international)
Typology of coastal and sea floor sediments / including petrology of hard rock substrate						
Grain size of coastal and sea floor sediments						
Mineralogy of coastal and sea floor sediments						
Geochemical parameters of the sea floor sediments						
Gases in the seafloor sediments (CH4, H2S, CO2, O2)						

35

Dynamics of the coastal zone and its management

36

Please provide more detailed information on the data collected for each parameter required of the assessment of the Ecological Quality Objectives according to your expertise

Parameters (as in BSIMAP 2017-22)	Data availability (select most appropriate) 1. Not able to collect data for 2. Recently implemented - no data yet 3. Sporadic / random data available 4. Good data availability	Time series (Please identify range of available data series)	Frequency of data collection (select most appropriate) 1. Annually 2. Seasonally 3. Monthly 4. Weekly 5. Daily 6. Hourly 7. Continuous 8. Other	Framework/Project (national – international)	N/A
Coast types (stable / erosional / accumulative)					
Erosion / accumulation yearly rate					
Types of coastal protection in areas affected by erosion (if any)					
Grain size and mineralogy of coastal sediments					
Topography and geomorphology of emerged and submerged beach					
Information (coastal morphology indicators)					
Level of risks of natural hazards in the coastal zone					
Coastal vulnerability					
Existence or not of coastal sediments budget management					

37

Can you please provide more information and possible links to known databases where the above mentioned data are stored?

38

Can you please provide more detailed information on the field and laboratory methodologies for obtaining data?

PARAMETER (as in BSIMAP 2017-22)	Monitoring station network (station grid)	Sampling area (region subregion etc., coastal, open sea)	Sampling Methodological standards	Field Sampling method (e.g. CTD) If possible add ref	Laboratory methods (e.g. fluorometric)	Framework/Project (national – international)
Coast types (stable / erosional / accumulative)						
Erosion / accumulation yearly rate						
Types of coastal protection in areas affected by erosion (if any)						
Grain size and mineralogy of coastal sediments						
Topography and geomorphology of emerged and submerged beach						
Information (coastal morphology indicators)						
Level of risks of natural hazards in the coastal zone						
Coastal vulnerability						
Existence or not of coastal sediments budget management						

39

Policy making

To the best of your knowledge the process of adapting National Policies to International requirements has been:

- Easy
- Difficult
- Other

Please define

To the best of your knowledge what have been the biggest difficulties during the adaptation process?

Do you find the Assessment Elements and the relevant indicators clear and easily transferable to policies?

Do you find the Assessment Elements and the relevant indicators clear and easily transferable to policies?

- Yes
- No

You can add more information here if you want

Assessment methodologies

Please provide detailed information on the assessment methodologies used for each of the BSIMAP descriptors according to your knowledge and expertise

DESCRIPTOR (as in BSIMAP 2017-22)	Methodology	Existing Threshold Values (yes or no and if possible add reference or link)	GES definition	Assessment Area (regional, subregional)	Frequency of reporting	Prior assessment reports
Populations of all commercially exploited fish and shellfish are within safe biological limits, exhibiting a population age and size distribution that is indicative of a healthy stock						
All elements of the marine food webs to the extent that they are known, occur at normal abundance and diversity and their reproductive capacity are ensure on long-term basis						
Biological diversity is maintained. The quality and occurrence of habitats and the distribution and abundance of species are in line with prevailing physlographic, geographic and climatic conditions. I) Stabilized or increasing trends of the populations of the threatened species						

41

Biological diversity is maintained, the quality and occurrence of habitats and the distribution and abundance of species are in line with prevailing physlographic, geographic and climatic conditions. II) Sea floor integrity is at a level that ensures that the structure and functions of the ecosystems are safeguarded and benthic ecosystems, in particular, are not adversely affected						
Biological diversity is maintained, the quality and occurrence of habitats and the distribution and abundance of species are in line with prevailing physlographic, geographic and climatic conditions. III) Permanent alteration of hydrographical conditions does not adversely affect marine ecosystems						
Non-Indigenous species introduced by human activities are at levels that do not adversely alter the ecosystems						

42

Human-induced eutrophication is minimised, especially adverse effects thereof, such as losses in biodiversity, ecosystem degradation, harmful algae blooms and oxygen deficiency in bottom waters						
Concentrations of contaminants are at levels not giving rise to pollution effects						
Contaminants in fish and other seafood for human consumption do not exceed levels established by regionally agreed values or other relevant standards						
Properties and quantities of marine litter do not cause harm to the coastal and marine						
Concentrations of contaminants are at levels not giving rise to pollution effects						
Sea-floor integrity is at a level that ensures that the structure and functions of the ecosystems are safeguarded and benthic ecosystems, in particular, are not adversely affected.						

43

Permanent alteration of hydrographical conditions does not adversely affect marine ecosystems.						
--	--	--	--	--	--	--

44

Concluding Remarks

Have you collaborated with other Black Sea countries in terms of data sharing and data mining or assessment?

- Yes
 No

Which Black Sea Countries have collaborated with?

- Bulgaria
 Georgia
 Republic of Moldova
 Romania
 Russian Federation
 Turkey
 Ukraine

If you have collaborated in the past, can you please describe the collaboration?

What are the most common hurdles you come across in terms of data collecting, mining, knowledge sharing and assessment?

Would you like to add anything or raise a point that is of particular importance and you would like us to discuss it during the consultation?

Name and contact information of colleagues that could be interested in participating.

*Thank you very much for your time and effort!
We really appreciate it!*

6. The Interviews Questionnaire

Questionnaire for Semi – Structured interviews to policy and science experts

Fields marked with* are mandatory.

Summary and Scope

This short semi – structured questionnaire has been created to accompany the stakeholders' consultation process on identifying the main needs of Black Sea countries for implementing environmental policies.

The overall scope of this activity will be to deliver harmonised methodologies for sampling, measurement analysis and modelling taking in to account best practices on the assessment of the ecological status of the Black Sea (BS). This scope will be achieved after a series of consultations (workshops, questionnaire survey, semi-structured interviews). The harmonisation of the regional research methods is dedicated to the development of compatible working methodologies for the Black Sea that will ensure that all data collection, analysis and storage processes respect policy requirements, international standards and best practices, as well as the FAIR principles.

The objective of these interviews is to validate through expert knowledge the results of the first survey on mapping the gaps and needs of the Black Sea policy makers and experts towards the above described goal.

The present questionnaire is an important step in receiving further feedback from you regarding the above inquires focusing on which Assessment Elements or Objectives can be assessed at a satisfactory level, what data are collected, how these are stored and managed, All this information will be helpful for prioritising the most pressing gaps and needs.

The present questionnaire is organised in 3 distinct sections:

1. Marine Environmental Policies Implementation Processes;
2. Assessment of gaps and needs;
3. Policy Making.

Respondents Information

(Personal data are for statistical use only and will not be disclosed to anyone beyond the person responsible for the survey. — Personal data will be destroyed once all analysis has been completed as described in the above data privacy statement)

A. Name

B. Surname

C. Email address

D. Date of Birth

E. Country of professional interest

- BG-Bulgaria
- GE-Georgia
- MD-Republic of Moldova
- RO-Romania
- TR-Turkey
- UA-Ukraine

F. Affiliation(Institution)

G. Years of expertise

H. Role in monitoring programs

Marine Environmental Policies Implementation Progress in Black Sea

Marine Environmental Policies and Programmes (as Black Sea Integrated Monitoring and Assessment Programme - BSIMAP, Water Framework Directive - WFD, Marine Strategy Framework Directive - MSFD, Blue Economy Policies, etc) base their implementation on monitoring programs to fulfil their objectives to be reached, in order to improve the Ecological Quality Status of the Black Sea. In this frame, specific monitoring guidelines and requirements for assessing data and status are needed.

The main task of such programs are to produce quality assured data for scientifically-based and validated criteria and indicators to be used by policy-makers, in this case consistent with the environmental quality objectives (EcoQOs) of the BSSAP (Black Sea Strategic Action Plan).

Most of the following questions are based on the format of the EcoQOs, descriptors and parameters, as set on the BLACK SEA INTEGRATED MONITORING AND ASSESSMENT PROGRAM for years 2017-2022(BSIMAP 2017-2022). However, these do not differ in essence from the Descriptor and Criteria used in the MSFD or in the Eos set by the UNEP/MAP or the other Regional Sea Conventions.

1. In your opinion what are the greatest challenges for BS ecosystems (current and anticipated):

2. To the best of your knowledge are the available data sufficient to assess current Status of BS ecosystem? (Yes/No – what is missing?)

3. In relation to the anticipated challenges? Are current monitoring schemes sufficient to cover the needs of future challenges? (Yes/No – what is missing?)

4. To the Best of your knowledge can the available data support the upcoming assessment of the Ecological quality objectives included in Black Sea Integrated Monitoring and Assessment Program and the MSFD Descriptors.

- All of the identified Ecological quality objectives.
- More than half of the Ecological quality objectives, but we are on track to complete by the end of this cycle
- Less than half of the Ecological quality objectives yet, but we are working on it.
- Very few and we are not sure we will reach our goal by the end of this cycle.
- I am not sure.

5. To the best of your knowledge among the Ecological Quality objectives / MSFD descriptors/ Blue Growth potential which are more difficult to evaluate? Based on the ability to monitor the required parameters.

Please select 1 to 5 according to the level of knowledge you are able to acquire for each of the objectives based on the ability to monitor the required parameters	1 (Least known)	2	3	4	5 (Most known)
The State of populations of all commercially exploited fish and shellfish.					
Abundance, diversity and reproductive capacity of all elements of the marine food webs to the extent that they are known.					
Coastal are a distribution and abundance of species in relation with prevailing physiographic, geographic and climatic conditions, quality and occurrence of habitats for the preservation of biodiversity.					
Sea floor distribution and abundance of species in relation with prevailing physiographic, geographic and climatic conditions, quality and occurrence of habitats for the preservation of Biodiversity).					
Impacts of introduced non-indigenous species on the BS ecosystems.					
Eutrophication and its effects on biodiversity, ecosystem degradation, possible presence of harmful algae blooms and oxygen deficiency in bottom waters.					
Concentrations of contaminants in sea water.					
Concentrations of contaminants in fish and other seafood for human consumption.					
Properties and quantities of marine litter.					
Level of noise and its impacts in the marine ecosystem.					
Renewable energy potential.					
Seafloor integrity is at a level that ensures that the structure and functions of the ecosystems are safeguarded and the benthic ecosystems, in particular, are not adversely affected.					
Permanent alteration of hydrographical conditions does not adversely affect marine ecosystems.					

6. Of the above responses, which would be your top priorities for improving monitoring capabilities?

7. Regarding the objectives that cannot be assessed, what is the reason? (Technical know-how, lack of monitoring ability, financial cost of monitoring, etc. ...)

- Technical difficulties related to monitoring
- Monitoring costs
- Inadequate time series
- Inadequate assessment methodology
- Lack of threshold values, GES definition etc
- Other (can you define?)

8. According to your opinion, what is needed in order to improve assessment sufficiency?

9. Do you feel that the above mentioned Assessment Elements cover all Black Sea assessment needs or more issues exist that you feel should be identified (for addressing current or future challenges)?

- Above mentioned objectives cover all concerns of the Black Sea
- No there are still concerns on the status of the Black Sea that are not being identified

10. Please Identify what you feel is missing to complete an assessment on the status of the Black Sea.

11. What you recognize as the critical gaps in scientific knowledge that may prevent informed decisions being

5

made about the current conditions of Black Sea ecosystems?

Assessment on gaps and needs for implementing environmental policies

12. How satisfied are you with the ability to assess the status of the coastal zone and the open sea, in the Black Sea region?

Please select 1 to 5 according to the level of knowledge you have, based on data availability
(1 for the least known and 5 for the most known).

	1	2	3	4	5
*Coastal Zone					
*Open Sea					

13. To the best of your knowledge how accessible are Black Sea data?

- Very easy to access
- Quite easy
- Not so easy
- Difficult
- Very difficult to access

14. When interested in assessing the environment of the Black Sea, where do you look for data?

- United Nations or other International databases
- EModNet and / or other European databases
- Black Sea Commission Database
- National databases
- University / research center's database
- Request from owners (past researchers)
- I don't know

15. To the best of your knowledge, how easy is it for you to access the available data?

- Most of the data are located in easy to use databases and can be downloaded.
- Some of the data can be downloaded, the rest are easily available upon request.
- Most of the data are in known locations, but are not easy to access.
- Most of the data are not accessible or their location is unknown.

16. There is a lot of discussion recently about data and methods harmonization. What is your opinion on that?

17. To the best of your knowledge what will be the biggest challenge for achieving harmonized monitoring and assessment methodologies in the Black Sea?

Policy making

18. To the best of your knowledge the process of adapting National Policies to International requirements has been:

- Easy
- Difficult
- Other

Please elaborate

19. To the best of your knowledge what have been the biggest difficulties during the adaptation process?

20. Do you find the Assessment Elements and the relevant indicators clear and easily transferable to policies?

- Yes
- No

21. Would you like to add any more information?

Concluding Remarks

22. Have you collaborated with other Black Sea countries in terms of data sharing and data mining or assessment?

- Yes
- No

23. Which Black Sea Countries have collaborated with?

- Bulgaria
- Georgia
- Republic of Moldova
- Romania
- Russian Federation
- Turkey
- Ukraine

24. If you have collaborated in the past with another BS country, can you please describe the collaboration?

25. What are the most common challenges you come across in terms of data collecting, mining, knowledge sharing and assessment?

26. Would you like to add anything or raise a point that is of particular importance and you would like us to discuss it during the consultation?

*Thank you very much for your time and effort!
We really appreciate it!*

7. Inventory of available data and methods

The inventory can be found at:

<https://doc.doorsblacksea.eu/remote.php/webdav/Data%20Availability%20Inventory.xls>

(for DOORS partners, because this link is password protected)

and/or

<https://cloudfs.hcmr.gr/index.php/s/3PnOSF6ZE9iaweC>